

Рамазанова Сона Мустафа,
Азербайджанский Государственный Аграрный Университет
Преподаватель, кафедра "Языков"
Алиева Айнура Акиф,
Азербайджанский Государственный Аграрный Университет
Преподаватель, кафедра "Языков"
Хамидли Нурай Тариэль
Азербайджанский Государственный Аграрный Университет
Преподаватель, кафедра "Языков"
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13369126>

ИСТОРИЯ АНГЛИЙСКОГО ЯЗЫКА. КАК БЫЛ СОЗДАН ЯЗЫК И КАК ОН ПРЕВРАТИЛСЯ В ГЛОБАЛЬНЫЙ ЯЗЫК?

Ramazanova Sona Mustafa,
Azerbaijan State Agrarian University
Lecturer, Department of Languages
Aliyeva Aynura Akif,
Azerbaijan State Agrarian University
Lecturer, Department of Languages
Hamidli Nuray Tariyel
Azerbaijan State Agrarian University
Lecturer, Department of Languages

THE HISTORY OF THE ENGLISH LANGUAGE - HOW WAS THE LANGUAGE CREATED AND HOW DID IT EVOLVE INTO A GLOBAL LANGUAGE?

Аннотация.

История языка охватывает все исторические изменения с момента возникновения языка. Изменения в языке, непосредственно связанные с внутренними процессами языка, называются лингвистическими, а изменения, связанные с общим развитием общества и историей народа, — экстралингвистическими факторами. Существует несколько причин, которые препятствуют или препятствуют формированию языка. Обращение к заимствованию слов связано с комплексом как внутрилингвистических, так и экстралингвистических причин. Экстралингвистические причины охватывают политические, экономические, социальные и культурные аспекты языковых отношений.

Необходимость назвать ранее неизвестные предметы и события часто приводит к заимствованию из другого языка как причине лингвистического заимствования.

Такие причины действительно немаловажны. В спектре экстралингвистических факторов нетривиальны такие соображения, как психологические, эстетические, эвфемистические выражения, а также исторические условия, играющие значительную роль в процессе заимствования слов, религиозная принадлежность и политическая ситуация в стране.

Язык и культура тесно переплетаются, всегда играя незаменимую роль в обогащении и развитии друг друга. Именно через такие взаимосвязи, причины, методы и историю влияния между языком и культурой литературные примеры предлагают наиболее прекрасный способ наблюдения.

Английский — это увлекательный язык, который развивался на протяжении веков и сегодня является одним из наиболее распространенных языков в мире. Английский язык имеет свои корни в англосаксонском, западногерманском языке, на котором говорили англосаксы, поселившиеся в Британии в V веке.

Самая ранняя форма английского языка была известна как староанглийский, на котором говорили примерно до 11 века. Среднеанглийский язык возник после нормандского завоевания 1066 года, и на нем говорили до конца 15 века. Современный английский начал развиваться в 16 веке и с тех пор продолжает развиваться.

Abstract.

The history of language encompasses all historical changes from the inception of language. Changes in language directly related to the internal processes of the language are called linguistic, while those related to the overall development of society and the history of the people are termed extralinguistic factors. There are several reasons that hinder or impede the formation of language. Resorting to borrowing words involves a complex of both intralinguistic and extralinguistic reasons. Extralinguistic reasons encompass political, economic, social, and cultural aspects of language relations.

The necessity to name previously unknown objects and events often leads to borrowing from another language as the reason for linguistic borrowing.

Such reasons are indeed not insignificant. Within the spectrum of extralinguistic factors, considerations such as psychological, aesthetic, euphemistic expressions, as well as historical conditions that play a significant role in the process of borrowing words, religious affiliation, and the political situation of the country, are not trivial.

Language and culture have been closely intertwined, always playing an indispensable role in enriching and developing each other. It is precisely through such interrelations, the reasons, methods, and history of influence between language and culture that literary examples offer the most beautiful way to observe.

English is a fascinating language that has evolved over the centuries, and today it is one of the most commonly spoken languages in the world. The English language has its roots in Anglo-Saxon, a West Germanic language spoken by the Anglo-Saxons who settled in Britain in the 5th century.

The earliest form of English was known as Old English, which was spoken until around the 11th century. Middle English emerged after the Norman Conquest of 1066, and it was spoken until the late 15th century. Modern English began to develop in the 16th century, and it has continued to evolve since then.

Ключевые слова: мультикультурализм, заимствования, экстралингвистика, язык, средневековье, литература, многообразие, Беовульф, викинги, Кентерберийские сказки.

Keywords: multiculturalism, borrowings, extralinguistic, language, medieval, literature, diversity, Beowulf, vikings, Canterbury tales

In our modern era, the English language has evolved into the language of political negotiations and business. Major scientific and medical research is also conducted in English. According to international agreements, air traffic controllers working on planes must know English. English is the most commonly taught language in schools in South America and Europe. Children in the Philippines and Japan begin learning English from a very young age. English is the official language of more than seventy-five countries, including Britain, Canada, the United States, Australia, and South Africa.

In countries where various languages are spoken, English often serves as the official state language to facilitate communication among people. India is a good example of this. In this country where 24 different languages are spoken, with each spoken by over a million people, English serves as a common language for everyone.

Where do the roots of the English language come from? Why has this language become so popular? To answer these questions, we need to take a historical excursion from the Black Sea in southeastern Europe to the northern regions, five thousand years ago.[1]

Experts say that people in this region spoke the Proto-Indo-European language. This language no longer exists, so experts do not know how it was pronounced. However, many European languages are based on the Proto-Indo-European language, including Ancient Greek, German, and Latin. Latin, as a spoken language, no longer exists. However, the roots of modern Spanish, French, and Italian languages lie in Latin. Ancient German played a significant role in the formation of Dutch, Danish, German, Norwegian, Swedish, and English.

The English language emerged as a result of invasions of the British Isles several hundred years ago. The invaders settled in territories along the northern shores of Europe.

The first invasions took place over fifteen hundred years ago by the Angles. The Angles were members of Germanic tribes who crossed the English Channel (La Manche). Later, members of two more tribes crossed into Britain. These were the Saxons and Jutes. These groups encountered the Celts who had been living in Britain for several thousand years. War broke out between the Celts and the invaders. In these wars, the majority of the Celts either died or were pushed back.

Some later migrated to places that became known as Wales. Over many years, a mixture of the languages spoken by the Saxons, Angles, and Jutes resulted in the formation of Old English, or Anglo-Saxon.[2]

Understanding Old English can indeed be quite challenging. Only a few experts can read sample texts in this ancient form of the English language. From this period, only a handful of written examples remain. One of these is the epic poem "Beowulf," dedicated to a heroic king. Researchers believe the poem dates back to the 7th or 8th centuries. The author of the poem remains unknown.

Approximately a thousand years ago, Britain was invaded again, this time from the north by the Vikings. Vikings from Denmark, Norway, and other northern countries sought to expand trade routes and find slave markets. They established temporary bases by consolidating power in certain regions. However, some of these bases were later fortified and transformed into permanent settlements. The Vikings settled in Britain as well. A number of words in the English language today are derived from the Vikings. For example, words like "sky," "leg," "egg," "crawl," "lift," and "take" come from the ancient languages of the northern peoples.

In 1066, Britain faced yet another invasion known in history as the Norman Conquest. This invasion was led by William the Conqueror. The Normans originated from Normandy in the north of France. They became the rulers of Britain and spoke French for several hundred years. At that time, educated individuals conversed in French, which was considered one of the most important languages. The language of common people remained the earlier form of Old English.[3]

In Old English, many words were indeed borrowed from the French language. For example, words like "damage," "prison," and "marriage" in English come from French. Additionally, several words related to laws and government in the English language were borrowed from the French spoken by the Normans. Examples of these words include "jury," "parliament," and "justice."

The French language used by Norman rulers had a significant impact on the English language spoken by people about eight hundred years ago. Experts refer to this period in the history of the language as Middle English. As time passed, the Normans could no longer speak authentic French. The language they used was a mixture of French and Middle English.

Middle English resembles modern English, but understanding it is very difficult today. Many written works from that period have survived. However, one of the most distinguished literary works of Middle English is "The Canterbury Tales," written by the poet Geoffrey Chaucer, who lived in London in the 1400s. The work is considered a collection of tales told in verse by various people traveling to the city of Canterbury.

English language experts consider Geoffrey Chaucer to be the greatest poet writing in English. They say that Chaucer's "The Canterbury Tales" created a true picture of the lives of people living in Britain at that time.[4]

Here are 5 interesting facts about the English language:

1. "The origin of the English language"

The origin of the English language comes from Northwestern Germany and the Netherlands. It is believed that the people living in these regions spoke the Proto-Indo-European language. However, the exact details of this language are not known. Modern English began to be used in England for the first time in the 14th century and continued to develop until the 1550s. The languages closest to English are Dutch and Western Flemish.

2. "The number of people speaking English."

English is the official language in 67 countries and 27 non-sovereign entities like Hong Kong. It is spoken as a first language by 339 million people and as a second language by 603 million people. In the United States of America, where English is spoken as a first language by many Americans, it is considered the official language. Despite being the dominant language since the colonization of the continent in the 17th century, English has never been formally declared as the national language.

3. "The rules of the English language."

The grammar and orthography of the English language largely adhere to standard rules. Dr. Johnson's Dictionary of 1755 established the grammar and orthographic rules of the English language. This dictionary is the first to comprehensively document the English language lexicon and is one of the most famous dictionaries in history, with its compilation taking more than 8 years.

4. The most commonly used adjective in English is "good."

The most commonly used adjective in the English language is "good." The most widespread noun in English is 'time', and the most commonly mispronounced (and often misspelled) word in English is 'pronunciation'.

5. "English is the language of the skies."

All pilots must communicate in English during international flights. Similarly, all air traffic controllers at international airports should be able to communicate with pilots in English.

After Old and Middle English comes the third stage of the English language, known as **Modern English**, which began in the 16th century and continues to the present day. This period is called Renaissance pe-

riod. The Renaissance (14th-17th centuries) saw a re-discovery of classical learning, which had a significant impact on English literature. During this time, the English language also borrowed many Greek and Latin words. The first English dictionary, A Table Alphabeticall of Hard Words, was published in 1604.[5]

The Modern English is conventionally defined as the English language since about 1450 or 1500. Distinctions are commonly drawn between the Early Modern Period (roughly 1450-1800) and Late Modern English (1800 to the present). The most recent stage in the evolution of the language is commonly called Present-Day English (PDE). However, as Diane Davies notes, "Linguists argue for a further stage in the language, beginning around 1945 and called 'World English,' reflecting the globalization of English as an international lingua franca," (Davies 2005).

"During the 15th century, a huge amount of change affected English pronunciation, spelling, grammar, and vocabulary, so that Shakespeare would have found Chaucer almost as difficult to read as we do. But between Jacobethan times and today the changes have been very limited.

One of the most famous examples of Early Modern English literature is William Shakespeare's play *Romeo and Juliet*, which was first performed in 1597. To this day, William Shakespeare is considered the greatest writer in the English language.

The King James Bible, which was first published in 1611, also had a significant impact on the development of Early Modern English. The Bible was translated into English from Latin and Greek, introducing many new words into the language.

The final stage of the English language is known as *Modern English*, which has been spoken from around the 19th century to the present day. Modern English has its roots in Early Modern English.

The most significant change occurred in the 20th century, with the introduction of mass media and technology. For example, new words have been created to keep up with changing technology, and old words have fallen out of use. However, the core grammar and vocabulary of the language have remained relatively stable.[2]

Today, English is spoken by an estimated 1.5 billion people around the world, making it one of the most widely spoken languages in the world. It is the official language of many countries, including the United Kingdom, the United States, and Australia. English is also the language of international communication and is used in business, education, and tourism.

Literature:

1. <https://upperedu.az/ingilis-dilinin-tarixi>
2. <https://www.amerikaninnesi.org/a/history-ofenglish/1573283.html>
3. [https://www.anl.az/down/meqale/bak/2019/01/733811\(meqale\).pdf](https://www.anl.az/down/meqale/bak/2019/01/733811(meqale).pdf)
4. <https://langster.org/en/blog/a-brief-history-of-the-english-language-from-old-english-to-modern-days/>
5. <https://www.thoughtco.com/modern-english-language-1691398>